

Preliminary evidence of advanced bio-based fertilizer production and water reuse from fishery wastes

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Abstract: Seafood processing generates a huge amount of discards that can be used to recover valuable compounds. In this study, a biorefinery scheme is proposed to obtain calcium carbonate (liming agent), protein hydrolysates (biostimulant), biogas and a biochar-compost composite. Water would be also reused within the process, minimizing water footprint. From this scheme, 1 ton of raw waste could be valorized in 700 kg of a liming agent, 30 kg of biostimulant, 26 kg of biochar-compost composite and 1.2 Nm³ of methane.

Keywords: Biochar; biorefinery; compost; mollusc; water reuse

Fishery plays a significant role for every country in the Adriatic basin. The largest catch, in 2007, was in Italy – 465,637 tons (Zonn *et al.*, 2021). Marine activities are highly relevant in the economy of Ancona (Italy) where the mollusc industry generates around 9830 t·y⁻¹ considering mussels, clams, murex, etc. Seafood processing is accompanied by the generation of tremendous amounts of by-products and discards. These non-edible residues contain a considerable amount of biomolecules such as proteins, polysaccharides, lipids, carotenoids, vitamins, minerals, etc., that can be recovered. Recovering these biomolecules can mitigate environmental problems associated with seafood processing (Bruno *et al.*, 2019) and close the loop in the mollusc industry. Depending on the kind of treatment, biowastes can be not only used to produce value-added chemicals (Nisticò, 2017) but also other processes (e.g., composting, incineration) can be applied to the by-products to obtain maximum productivity in a biorefinery scheme (Figure 1.1).

The Mollusc industry's wastes result in two different fractions that must be separated to optimize the recovery of added-value compounds: 67-85% of the total waste, depending on the mollusc species, consists of shells and only 15-33% is the residual meat. Shells have a low moisture content (<8%) and involve mainly inorganic compounds (>94% of ashes). On the other hand, the residual meat has only 19-28 % of dry matter and its organic fraction accounts for 74-89% (Table 1.1).

Prior mixing of the solid waste with water is needed. Batch experiments were carried out at different waste to water (W:W) ratios (1:0.3, 1:1, 1:1.5, 1:2, weight:weight). The mollusc waste came from a company set in Ancona and was composed by clam (79%), mussel (13%) and murex (8%). After shredding, the raw sample was separated into two fractions: crushed shells settled at the bottom of the tank (recovered shells); and a liquid fraction composed of the added water and the residual meat and lighter particles that came out from shredding. W:W ratio did not influence the separation efficiency, i.e., the organic matter of the recovered shell did not show a great variation along different tests (Figure 1.2). Since the downstream hydrolysis step (Figure 1.1) requires a substrate (residual meat) to water (S:W) ratio of 1:2, the W:W ratio equal to 1:0.3, which is equivalent to the former, was selected.

Recovered shells showed $86.5 \pm 3.2\%$ of dry matter and volatile content of $3.3 \pm 0.8\%$ d.b.. Being highly rich in calcium carbonate (more than 80% d.b.), once dried and milled, shells could be used as an alternative to the mineral calcium carbonate obtained by a quarry, with a very low environmental footprinting. This product is certainly of interest, considering that the European median pH is 5.8 for Ap soil (0-20 cm topsoil) (Fabian *et al.*, 2014).

Regarding the liquid stream, valuable biomolecules can be recovered. This stream presented $71.0 \pm 6.6\%$ d.b. of organic matter, being proteins $30.0 \pm 2.1\%$ d.b.. To recover protein hydrolysates, 0.01 ml of Alcalase enzyme was added per g of substrate. After 4 hours of stirring at a controlled temperature (40-60°C), the liquid, rich in peptides and amino acids, was concentrated and used as a biostimulant for horticulture, while the produced condensate (water stream) was reused for further separation steps (Figure 1.1).

Due to its high organic content, the solid residue from hydrolysis could be used for biogas production through anaerobic digestion. The digestate could be then composted and/or pyrolyzed to obtain compost and biochar, respectively. Biochar and compost present significant potential for soil C sequestration. The biochar-compost blending would enhance the composting performance by adding more stable C and creating a value-added product (biochar-compost blend) that can offset potential negative effects of the composting system and of the pyrolysis biochar system (Oldfield *et al.*, 2018).

To conclude, the biorefinery scheme developed in this study (based on circular economy principles) allowed transforming wastes from the mollusc industry into nutrients and other value-added products for crops; specifically, 1 ton of raw waste could be valorized in 700 kg of a liming agent, 30 kg of biostimulant, 26 kg of biochar-compost composite and 1.2 Nm³ of methane. In addition, water could be mostly reused from the process, minimizing water footprint.

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Table 1.1 Chemical characterization of mollusc by-products.

Parameter	Unit of measure	meat residue	shell fraction
DM	%	23.66±4.56	93.02±0.59
pH	-	5.9±0.5	8.5±0.1
Ashes	%	23.5±85.9	95.9±11.5
crude protein	%	52.1±79.3	1.6±0.5
fats	%	22.6±34.9	-
P	g/kg db	8.69±1.08	0.41±0.2
Na	g/kg db	15.85±2.85	6.11±1.24
Mg	g/kg db	3.20±1.31	0.47±0.16
K	g/kg db	9.40±0.21	0.42±0.23
Ca	g/kg db	41.7±14.5	347.5±13.6

Figure 1.1 Scheme of the proposed biorefinery from mollusc waste.

Figure 1.2 Variation of the organic content of the recovered shell according to the W:W used for shredding.